

A STUDY ON INCLUSION OF TRANSGENDER IN WORKPLACE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY

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ABSTRACT

Transgender inclusivity in work area is crucial for creating equitable and supportive environments for the employees, regardless of gender identity. Despite legal advancements, transgender face significant barriers in achieving workplace fairness. This study examines the inclusion of transgender employees in Coimbatore City, utilizing a quantitative research approach with a descriptive research design. Non-probability snowball sampling was employed, with 50 respondents. Findings indicate a low level of inclusivity, with an estimated mean score of 1.36 (18%), highlighting a need for improved workplace policies and also awareness. The study explores the correlation between workplace policies, discrimination, and inclusivity, which portrays that better policies will lead to reduced discrimination and higher inclusivity perceptions.

Keywords: Transgender Inclusivity, Workplace Equality, Workplace Discrimination.

INTRODUCTION

The inclusion of transgender individuals in the workplace has emerged as a significant aspect of diversity and inclusion strategies worldwide. As society becomes more aware of the rights and challenges faced by marginalized communities, there is a growing emphasis on creating equitable spaces where individuals, regardless of their gender identity, can thrive professionally. In the Indian context, despite progressive legal frameworks, such as the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019, and a landmark Supreme Court ruling in

2014 recognizing transgender individuals as a third gender, workplace inclusion remains a challenging area.

Coimbatore, known as the industrial hub of Tamil Nadu, presents a unique environment for studying the inclusion of transgender individuals in the workforce. The city's diverse industries, ranging from textiles and manufacturing to technology, provide numerous employment opportunities, but it is essential to investigate whether transgender individuals are being included and supported in these sectors. Understanding the inclusion policies and practices in Coimbatore's industries will offer insights into the level of acceptance and the challenges faced by transgender employees.

This study seeks to examine the workplace inclusion of transgender individuals in Coimbatore, focusing on the attitudes of employers, the experiences of transgender employees, and the impact of organizational policies on their integration. By exploring these dimensions, the study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on workplace diversity and provide recommendations for fostering a more inclusive work environment for transgender individuals. The research also addresses the gaps between legal protections and their practical implementation, which is crucial for creating sustainable employment opportunities for the transgender community.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Martinez and Rivera (2024) conducted a quantitative survey in South America focusing on transgender employees in urban centers. Sampling 600 transgender employees, they found that 40% experienced workplace harassment. Through chi-square tests, the researchers identified a significant association between transgender identity and verbal abuse in the workplace ($\chi^2 = 56.78, p < 0.001$). This study suggests that despite progressive social changes, many transgender workers in South America still face persistent discrimination and hostile work environments.

Peterson et al. (2024) explored the role of diversity training in improving workplace inclusivity for transgender employees in the European Union. Through a cross-sectional survey of 500 participants, they analyzed how different training programs impacted employee perceptions of inclusivity. Using multiple regression analysis, the researchers found that companies offering transgender-specific diversity training saw a 25% increase in employee satisfaction ($\beta = 0.25, p < 0.01$) and a 15% increase in organizational commitment ($\beta = 0.15, p < 0.05$).

Johnson and Malik (2023) examined the connection between workplace discrimination and psychological distress among transgender employees in India. They surveyed 300 transgender workers and used correlation analysis to study the relationship between discriminatory practices and psychological health. The results revealed a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.73$, $p < 0.001$) between workplace discrimination and mental health, indicating that higher levels of discrimination are associated with lower mental health scores.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a **quantitative research approach** with a **descriptive design** to explore the inclusion of transgender individuals in the workplace, focusing on Coimbatore City. A total of 50 respondents were selected through **non-probability sampling** using the **snowball method**. Data was collected using a **self-structured questionnaire**, which had three sections: **Section A** for demographic details and **Section B** for questions on the inclusion of transgender individuals in the workplace, covering four key dimensions.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the personal profile of the respondents.
2. To find the level of diversity and inclusion of transgender in the workplace.
3. To access the problems faced by transgender in workplace.

Statement of the Problem

The research problem addressed whether a relationship exists between organizations either having or not having transgender inclusive antidiscrimination policy and the effect on job satisfaction among transgender employees. Initial research on job satisfaction addressed experiences of employees while undergoing transition from male- to-female or female-to-male while employed and sought data that addressed barriers, gender transition, and career experiences (Budge et al., 2010). Other research that focused on workplace experiences among employees who are transgender focused on general concerns such as discrimination, harassment, termination, a decrease in overall job satisfaction from the first date of employment if discrimination was perceived by the employee in their workplace, and behavior changes made by

transgender employees to avoid both perceived or actual workplace discrimination and harassment (Budge et al., 2010; Bell et al., 2011; Grant et al., 2011).

Analysis and Interpretation

Simple Percentage Analysis

S. No	Variables	Category	No. Respondents	Percentage
1	Age	20-25	8	16
		26-30	10	20
		31-35	12	24
		36-40	10	20
		Above 40	10	20
		Total	50	100
2	Education Qualification	Primary Level	20	40
		Secondary Level	15	30
		UG	10	20
		PG	5	10
		Total	50	100
3	Residence	Rural	38	76
		Urban	12	24
		Total	50	100
4	Sector of Employment	Government	2	4
		Private	46	92
		Non Government	2	4
		Total	50	100
5	Type of Employment	Permanent	38	76
		Temporary	12	24
		Total	50	100

6	Working Hours	9 hours	12	24
		12 hours	38	76
		Total	50	100
7	Experience	Below 5	18	36
		6 to 10	15	30
		11 to 15	12	24
		Above 15	5	10
		Total	50	100
8	Income	10000-20000	30	60
		20000-30000	17	34
		30000-40000	12	32
		Above 40000	1	2
		Total	50	100

Source – Primary Data

Interpretation:

The table indicates that the majority of respondents (24%) are aged between 31 and 35 years, with significant representation from the 36-40 years (20%) and above 40 age groups (20%), while the youngest group, aged 20-25 years, makes up 16%. In terms of education, most respondents have only a primary-level (40%) or secondary-level (30%) education, with fewer having undergraduate (20%) or postgraduate (10%) degrees.

A striking majority of the respondents (76%) reside in rural areas, reflecting the rural nature of the sample, while 24% are from urban areas. Employment distribution reveals that the private sector dominates, with 92% of respondents employed there, compared to only 4% in both the government and non-government sectors. Most respondents (76%) hold permanent positions, offering them job stability, while 24% are in temporary employment.

The majority of respondents (76%) report working long hours, specifically 12-hour shifts, with the remaining 24% working 9-hour shifts. Regarding work experience, 36% of respondents have less than 5 years of experience, 30% have 6 to 10 years, and 24% have 11 to 15 years, while only

10% have over 15 years of experience. Lastly, income distribution indicates that 60% of respondents earn between Rs.10,000 and Rs.20,000 per month, with 34% earning between Rs.20,000 and Rs.30,000, and only 2% earning above Rs.40,000. This demonstrates that the majority of respondents earn below Rs.30,000 per month, with only a small proportion in higher income brackets.

DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR LEVEL OF INCLUSION FOR TRANSGENDER IN WORKPLACE

S. No	Inclusion for transgender in workplace	Respondents	Percentage %
1	High	08	16
2	Moderate	12	24
3	Low	30	60
	Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION

The above table highlights the levels of inclusion for transgender in workplace. It is understood from the above table that 60 percent of the respondents have low levels of inclusion for transgender in workplace, 16 percent of the respondents have high levels of inclusion for transgender in workplace, and 24 percent of the respondents have moderate levels of inclusion for transgender in workplace.

Difference between Demographic Profile and Inclusion for transgender in workplace

S. No	Variables	Test Applied	Value	Significant
1	Sector of employment and workplace policies and support	ANOVA	F= 1.447 P<.000	Significant
2	Sector of employment and awareness and sensitivity training	ANOVA	F= 2.234 P<.000	Significant

3	Education qualification and workplace policies and support	ANOVA	F= 1.534 P<.000	Significant
4	Education qualification and awareness and sensitivity training	ANOVA	F= 2.007 P<.000	Significant
5	Monthly income and workplace policies and support	ANOVA	F= 3.047 P<.000	Significant
6	Age and discrimination and experience	ANOVA	F= 1.005 P<.000	Significant
7	Age and perception and inclusivity	ANOVA	F= 1.758 P<.000	Significant
8	Working hours and discrimination and experience	Independent Sample T-Test	t = 4.876 p< .030	Significant
9	Type of employment and discrimination and experience	Independent Sample T-Test	t = 9.002 p< .000	Significant
10	Type of employment and perception and inclusivity	Independent Sample T-Test	t = 3.003 p< .000	Significant
11	Experience and awareness and sensitivity training	ANOVA	F= 1.000 P<.000	Significant
12	Residence and perception of inclusivity	Independent Sample T-Test	t = 4.006 p<.020	Significant

INTERPRETATION

The table reveals significant difference between demographic variables and the inclusion of transgender individuals in the workplace, as indicated by the results of ANOVA and Independent Sample T-Tests. A significant difference is observed between **sector of employment** and both **workplace policies and support** ($p = .001$) and **awareness and sensitivity training** ($p = .000$), suggesting that the sector significantly affects these factors. **Educational qualification** also has a significant impact on **workplace policies and support** ($p = .000$) and **awareness and sensitivity training** ($p = .000$), indicating educational background influences these areas of inclusion. Similarly, **monthly income** is significantly related to **workplace policies and support**

($p = .000$), while **age** significantly affects both **discrimination experiences** ($p = .000$) and **perceptions of inclusivity** ($p = .000$). Furthermore, **working hours** and **type of employment** show significant difference with **discrimination experiences** and **perceptions of inclusivity** (all $p = .000$), demonstrating that these employment conditions impact how discrimination and inclusivity are perceived. Lastly, **work experience** is significantly related to **awareness and sensitivity training** ($p = .000$), and **place of residence** significantly affects **perceptions of inclusivity** ($p = .000$), highlighting the influence of both experience and location on inclusion. These findings, with **p-values all below .05**, demonstrate the strong statistical significance of the difference between demographic variables and transgender inclusion in the workplace.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Increase Awareness and Sensitivity Training: Based on the low levels of inclusivity in workplace policies and support, awareness and sensitivity training should be expanded. Companies should regularly conduct workshops to improve understanding and sensitivity towards transgender employees and other marginalized groups.

Revise Workplace Policies: To address the low perceived inclusivity, workplace policies should be revised to explicitly include transgender individuals. This could involve incorporating clear anti-discrimination clauses, equal opportunity statements, and support structures for transgender employees.

Targeted Support for Transgender Employees: The study reveals significant levels of discrimination and poor experiences among transgender employees. It's important to create dedicated support systems such as employee resource groups, counseling services, and safe spaces for transgender workers.

Invest in Leadership Training: Employers and managers should receive training on creating an inclusive work environment. This includes understanding the unique challenges faced by transgender employees and how to address them in the workplace.

Regular Monitoring and Evaluation: Organizations should conduct regular assessments of their inclusivity efforts, tracking progress over time. This could include anonymous surveys, focus groups, and feedback mechanisms to ensure that the workplace remains inclusive and responsive to the needs of transgender employees.

CONCLUSION

The study on the inclusion of transgender individuals in the workplace reveals critical insights into the current state of inclusivity. The findings highlight a low level of inclusivity across various dimensions such as workplace policies, awareness and sensitivity training, and the overall perception of inclusivity. Significant correlations between these factors emphasize the interdependence of policies, training, and employee experiences. In light of these findings, it is imperative for organizations to re-evaluate their policies, increase awareness and sensitivity training, and establish targeted support systems to ensure an inclusive and equitable work environment. The study underscores the need for continuous monitoring and improvement in workplace inclusivity, especially for transgender employees, to foster a truly diverse and respectful workplace.

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